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THE BRAZILIAN PRISON SYSTEM FROM THE FOUCAULTIAN PERSPECTIVE

AUTHOR

• Ísis Vasconcelos Morais Gomes
isismvasconcelos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Brazilian Constitution guarantees, as one of the fundamental rights, that no one will be held that harms the dignity of the human person (art. 5, XLVIII), but the detention houses (penitentiaries) are overcrowded, unhealthy and without the minimum condition for resocialization.